

Energy Harvesting from Raindrops

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Introduction

Energy Harvesting

- Energy harvesting is in this area not for large-scale energy production.
- The goal is to harvest enough energy to avoid the usage of cables and maintenance in remote places.
- The devices can extract energy from very small vibrations such as those created by a raindrop through piezo technology.

Our concept

Our concept is to get energy from raindrops with the help of a piezo electric generator. The device can be seen in the picture below:

The idea behind is that the chamber will be filled with a fluid or gas and covered with a membrane. When a droplet hits the membrane the shock wave will be transmitted to the piezo electric generator which will generate an electrical signal due to the piezo electric effect.

In our project we have been studying which parameters are important for maximizing the energy output. To do this we connected a piezoresistive pressure sensor to our device so that we indirectly could measure the momentum transmitted from the droplet to the sensor.

Experiments

Set up

The structures shown on some of the images was the base of the setup. The wires attached is the piezo sensor and the air/water entrance to the chamber. Other than this we used a syringe in a syringe pump. This was levelled to a height around one meter and the drops was released onto the membrane

Figure 1: When a drop hits the membrane it begins to oscillate which can be seen on the picture

Theory

For converting the pressure registered by the sensor to a momentum we used the following formula:

$$p = A \cdot t \cdot \sum P \quad (1)$$

p is the momentum, t is the time, A is the area of the sensor head and P is the measured pressure.

About the experiments

To investigate what parameters was important for maximise the energy we designed a couple of experiments.

- To test the linearity of the energy vs. the drop release height.
- To confirm that the more mass a drop has the more energy is gained.
- To test how the period could be changed by changing the drop height and the medium in the chamber.
- To test what the frequency of the drop rate means for the energy.
- To give an estimate of the energy gained based on the momentum registered

Conclusion

What we discovered:

- That there is a critical height at which most energy is gained.
- The medium in the chamber is important for the frequency that the membrane oscillates at.
- The medium is also important for how much energy is transmitted to the sensor.
- The needle type at the syringe has something to do with the energy due to how the drops are formed depends on the needle.
- The efficiency was found to be around 24% and the energy was estimated to be around $20 \mu\text{J}$ which is in the same range as what other scientists have gained[1].

So we can conclude that it is possible to get energy out from a raindrop but right now the technology is still very new so it still needs a lot of research before it is usable.

References

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